

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B109
Date: 08 Jul 2005
Take Off: 10:00:41
Landing: 14:44:11
Flight Time: 4h43m30s

Campaign: CLOPAP
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Norfolk, offshore and Suffolk

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Leeds University
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	CVI/CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
8	AMS	Jonny Crozier	Manchester University
9	WAS/PAN	Jim Hopkins	York University
10	WAS training	Ruth Boddy	York University
11	Peroxide	Brian Bandy	UEA
12	Noxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
13	PTRMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B109 Track 08-JUL-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b109
 Date: 8/7/05
 Project: CLOPAP
 Location: East Anglia + offshore

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
094035		inu to nav	0.18 kft	127	
094042		engine start	0.18 kft	127	
094258		power c/o	0.18 kft	127	
094528		taxy start	0.18 kft	127	
100041		T/O	0.17 kft	031	from cranfield
100745		asp open	6.1 kft	062	
102900	104050	Profile 1	11.0 - 2.9 kft	076	
103448		Profile 1	5.0 kft	077	interrupt
103633		Profile 1	5.0 kft	271	resume
105521	105716	Profile 2	2.0 - 0.09 kft	015	coltishall approach
110813	112219	Run 1	1.5 kft	318	
112656	114046	Run 2	2.5 - 3.0 kft	105	
114622	115729	Run 3	4.0 kft	300	
120541	121033	Profile 3	7.0 - 1.7 kft	142	
121033	121758	Run 4	1.7 - 2.5 kft	113	
122246	123454	Run 5	1.7 kft	299	
124036	125233	Run 6	5.5 - 6.3 kft	107	
125318	125900	Profile 4	6.3 - 1.7 kft	112	
130053	130207	Profile 5	1.4 - 0.89 kft	247	
130509	131731	Run 7	0.93 - 1.0 kft	300	
132403	133609	Run 8	2.4 kft	109	
134142	135326	Run 9	4.0 kft	309	
135828	141039	Run 10	6.5 - 9.0 kft	112	
143510		asp closed	5.9 kft	247	
144411		Land	0.15 kft	028	at cranfield
145034		standstill	0.15 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B109 Track 08-JUL-05

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 5 (draft 2 : prepared by K.N. Bower / T.W.Choularton)

Flight Number : B109

Date: Friday 9th July 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

CLOPAP Sortie Aims:

To study the evolution of aerosol in an urban plume as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol and gases with cloud both as the aerosol/gas modifies the cloud microphysics and the cloud modifies the aerosol and gases.

CLOPAP Sortie Location:

The plan is to fly in the region off the North Coast of East Anglia to investigate the interaction between aerosol and cloud over the North Sea. As winds will be from the NE, the transects will be from NW to SE and of about 12 minutes duration to avoid danger areas. One stack will be performed offshore, the second stack, shifting to the East over Norwich and the third as far to the SW of Norwich as possible avoiding the London control area.

CLOPAP Sortie Summary:

The case studies will be carried out by flying a series of transects across the wind (from NW to SE) within the boundary layer (one below cloud, and at least one in cloud) and one in the lower free troposphere immediately above cloud top. Each of these sets of transects will be immediately preceded by a vertical profile extending into the lower free troposphere starting from as close to the surface as possible (not below 1000 ft over land). These profiles will establish the vertical mixing and structure of the sampled air and establish the optimum altitudes for the following transects. This flight pattern will be repeated at intervals so that one is over the sea, one is above Norwich and one downwind of Norwich. Runs may be cut down to a minimum length of 12 minutes

CLOPAP Sortie Detail:

1. Take off and climb to FL 110 for transit at cruise speed to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent carrying out NO_x calibration at that level)
2. When in operating area over the North Sea to the north of the N Coast of East Anglia descend to minimum safe altitude below cloud. Perform a profile ascent by climbing at 1000 ft per minute to pass through cloud and to an altitude 200 ft above cloud top/ boundary layer top.
3. Descend to below cloud base, proceed across wind in the boundary layer until outside the plume as detected by CN counter/gases. Mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect. Perform a straight and level run (SLR) below cloud base (200 ft below cloud base) across wind and of length 84 km[#]. CCN measurements should commence at the start of this run. Core Chemistry calibrations should be carried out at start of run (as required) and completion announced so that WAS sampling can begin.
4. Ascend to the middle of the cloud layer. Turn through 180 degrees. Mission Scientist to announce in cloud transect (AMS to switch to CVI inlet) and perform SLR of length 84 km[#].
5. Ascend to 200 feet above cloud top turn through 180 degrees - mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect (AMS to return to Rosemount inlet). Perform a SLR of length 84 km[#]. CCN measurements should also commence at the start of this run.
6. Ascend to cruising altitude to transit to 50 km downwind and repeat steps 2 to 6
7. Continue repetitions until available flight time in science area is exhausted. NB transit distance between 2nd and subsequent stacks will be adjusted over land to avoid encroachment into restricted airspace.
8. Climb to transit level to return to home base (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 6 (Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud) : TWC/KNB

CLOPAP Scientific Aims

1. To investigate the evolution of an urban plume as it is advected away from the source region in cloudy conditions[#]. Changes in chemical speciation and the partitioning of species between the gas and particulate phases will be investigated.
2. To measure the changes in the size distribution and Cloud Condensation Nucleus (CCN) activity spectrum of the aerosol.
3. To measure changes in cloud microphysics as the aerosol properties in the plume, particularly those of the sub-set of aerosol acting as CCN.
4. To investigate the differences in the composition of aerosol that form cloud droplets and those that remain unactivated and interstitial to the cloud, and to observe how this changes as the plume ages.
5. To investigate the role of vertical exchange between the boundary layer and the free troposphere to understand its effect on the transport of aerosols and trace gases on the cloudy plume.

CLOPAP Weather Conditions

A stratocumulus capped boundary layer forming over land or sea downwind of a main source of urban air pollution. Limited convective penetration of the boundary layer top is acceptable (but not deep convection). The cloud cover should exceed 70% in the study areas.

CLOPAP Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

Cloud Physics

- **FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP**, Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high/low concentrations,
- **ADA and CPI** – as above
- **CCN** - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample and spectrum per run, if possible.
- **J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC**. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- **TWC** – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

Chemistry Measurements

WAS - 2 bottle samples per 100km flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist (first sample to be collected after core chemistry calibrations are completed).

NO_x, Ozone, SO₂, CO, PTRMS, Hydrogen peroxide to operate continuously.

AMS - to be operated on **Rosemount inlet** out of cloud, **CVI** inlet in cloud. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed or after take-off. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight or before landing.

Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rearward facing.

CCN measurements :alleviator should be filled at the start of cloud free passes.

Bottle filling (and **filter sampling**[#] if available) should occur in clear air transects only. Three[#] bottle samples should be filled during each boundary layer transect and 1 during the free troposphere transect. The Mission scientist will indicate when in plume using CN and selected gas measurements. All other instruments should run continuously.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KETIN BOWER

ELOPAPS

Flight No **B109**.....

Date 08/07/05.....

Page 1 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:11:27	NOXY	FL110	69	54.4/0.1E	NO ₂ cal start -2.85°C/-8.55°C 11mb/19° 665
					Cloud broken to RWS - South of Norwich
10:24:00					North of Norwich - Cloud to RWS - broken - ahead
					Stomached
10:24:54	NOXY	FL110	76	52.7/1.5E	-2.67 /-8.92°C Bmb/37° 669mb 248kt
					Got Cu below SCu. now
10:28:29		FL110			NO ₂ cal complete - just into cloud. Alto stratus
10:29:03	PI ↓				Non broken profile seen
10:30:20					9650 out of cloud layer
10:34:47	PI int	5000'		52.8/2.4E	6.6°C/4.71°C 11mb/22° 842mb
10:36:35	PI rec ↓		274	52.7/2.4E	
					(SO ₂ off today) Cloud looking
	PI	3200'			No cloud here - but cloud higher around us
10:38:59	PI		276	52.7/2.1E	SO ₂ increasing
10:40:35	PI cont	1300'			Still in cloud - safe alt - no lower
10:44:50					Climbing to 3000' - Will do missed approach
					to Colchester. overhead
10:46:29		3000'	231	52.8/1.5E	
10:50:00					Bear above CT for part of this '3000'
10:50:50		3000			1015 QFE
10:51:15					Turning RPT. and descending
10:53:25		2000'			In cloud - /not in cloud
10:54:30				52.6/1.2E	gap - 8mb to overhead

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci: KEITH BOWE

Flight No **B109**.....

Date 06/02/05.....

Page 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:55:17	P2 st	2000'	29	52.6/1.2	Broken cloud - Start Point
					10kts str wind CB 800-900'
10:57:18	P2 end	200'			will climb to 900' to transit to A
10:58:10					900' too low - undred again - ↑1500'
11:01:42	Trans	1500'	111	52.8/1.7E	Summit to CVI - AMC inlet
					4 on CCN (AMS) - also on CVI CCN
11:06:00					FFSP - seeing perhaps new
11:07:10					P pump off - 0.2
					EF dt - ^{AMS} 2300 2600
11:08:12	R1 st	1500'	316	52.8/2.0E	1500 on 1013 → 1700' In cloud now
11:09:13	R1				In a gap between two layers of cloud.
11:11:12					CCN start - (AMS to Rosemont @ 11:12:00)
11:12:43	R1	1500			AMS back on Rosemont
11:14:37					AMS seeing hints of cirrostratus
					CT below ~ 900' - too low to fly in
11:17:20	R1	1500	303	53.0/1.2E	6 min request for CCN - permission done.
					Broken Cloud Below - it's very low indeed to str.
11:20:09	R1	1500	300	53.1/1.0E	Passing point B
11:20:19	R1 end				CCN complete
					FAAM CPC ~ 3x higher than UM157.
					level at 2000' → 2250
11:29:31					climbers to 2500'
11:26:55	R2	2500	115		2700 Real Alt 11:03/9.08°C 8m/s/29' 92 rmb
11:27:54	R2	2500	113	53.1/1.0E	CCN somewhat grabs ← Circ Chem Cals started
11:28:59					Point B - still out of cloud CB coming down to meet us
11:29:55	R2	2500		53.0/1.1E	Chem cals done

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CLOPAPS

Flight No **B109**.....

Date **08/07/05**.....

Page **3** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:31:44	R2				gently climbing to 3000'
11:32:30	R2	3000'			still not yet in cloud
11:33:27	R2	3000'			CEN spectrum complete -
11:37:43	R2	3000'			through cloud AMS - 200 CVI sky d d
					217kts 907 mb 10.4/9.68° 9m/s/46°
11:35:55	R2	3000'	119	52.9/1.6	ON 160 cm ² AMS, φ on CVI ??
					✓ CEN spectrum done again 2D reports little cloud
11:40:46	R2 end	3000'		52.7/2.1	turning RMT. and climb to cloud base
11:44:30					AMS on Rosemead Nav.
11:45:30		4000		52.7/2.1	873 mb 8.83
					On SCu embedded
11:46:21	R3	4000	299	52.7/2.0	874 mb 8.36/7.92°C 11m/s/59° 222kt
					more cloud on this run than the includ run 2D
11:49:20					3mg NO ₃ CPC-2000-5000'
11:50:00	R3	4000	303	52.9/1.6	Out of cloud base now 874 mb 8.66/7.03
11:51:52					Just going into another bit of cloud
11:55:23					CEN spectrum done - Cloud unambiguously
11:57:28	R3 end	4000	293	53.1/1.0E	climbing to 7000' @ B
12:00:35		7000'	209	52.9/0.8	
					CN 20000 (AMS) SO ₄ from AMS
12:05:00					- O ₃ 3mg - 0.3 SO ₄
12:05:40	P3 start	7000	105		Profile descent to 1700' (D → C)
12:07:50		4800	111	52.6/0.8E	CT at 4700
12:10:31	P3 end	R4 1700	112	52.5/1.0	Start Run 2 in cloud - 10.77/11.84
12:11:26					AMS on CVI

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KETH BOWER

CLOPPAS.

Flight No **B.109**.....

Date 05/07/05.....

Page 4 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:12:40	wh				climbing to safe Alt.
14:31					
					lets
					At tops of embedded Cu.
12:16:00	wh				Crossed plume -
12:17:57	end R4	2500			end of run
12:20:27		1700			level out 1700 - 2 mins to start of run
					WAS start bottle sample -
12:22:46	R5	1700'	301	52.5/1.5	2 min start of run 951mb 11.37°/11.5° (AMS, NO _x ⇒ plume) WAS flying 10mb/s
12:26:34	R5	1700'	300	54.4/1.5	South of Norech - Notherly wind
					Come out of cloud - broken cloud beneath
12:34:54	R5 end	1700		52.6/0.6	End run at D - climb to 6000
12:37:00		5500			AMS on Rosemont - start at 5500' above
12:37:40		5500			Cre Chem Cals. started
					T/Td 6.18
					↑ NO ₂ no increase in NO _x
12:40:00		5500			CEN sample started
12:40:35	R6	5500			Run Start - Cre Chem Cals Done WAS ✓
12:42:20		5500			In Cloud top - bottle cut - ease up to 6000'
12:42:30	R6	6000			
12:45:44	R6	6000	113	52.5/1.0E	10m/s / 40°, 43.1°/4.46°, 811 mb 0.4/0.1 mg/m ³ SO ₂ /NO ₂ AMS 1.0 Avg. NO _x - pretty low - flat.
12:49:57		6000			Creeping up a little to 6340' to avoid cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.109**.....

 Date **08/07/05**.....

 Page **5** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:52:20	R6				CCN - few problems - resetting
12:52:35	R6 end	6300	112	52.3/1.7	4.36/3.54° 10 m/s / 40° 807 mb ↓
12:53:18	P4 start				⊙ → E profile descent to try to get below cloud in a safe area - to do a below cloud run E → F
					Another CT at 4000' (had less! CCN run)
12:57:20		2150			large water drops 2D
12:59:00	P4 end	1400			in cloud still - will climb back up
13:00:00		2300			Can now see the sea. 2300-500
13:00:51	P5 st	1400	247	51.9/1.6	i
13:02:09	P5 end	1000			14.25/10.29° 9 m/s / 27° 978
13:05:00					just by Echecher
13:05:09	R7 st	1000			E-F
					Core Chem also complete
					CCN, was - told to start sample area (and
					AMS 0.3/0.3/ - CN 2000 spike over crest
					NO _x spike too
					CN spike - NO _x too - smoke plume PHS
					MP monitored on PHS
13:17:38	R7 end	1000			Carriage at 10' velocity - a/p.
13:18:39					Climbing to 2500'
13:19:08					1700 into cloud, in/out " " "
13:19:30					AMS on CVI w/dt
13:21:00		2500'	147	52.2/0.0	level at 2500
					No core down and req

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.109**.....

 Date **08/07/05**.....

 Page **6** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:24:03	R8	2500	112	52.2/0.3E	Q&M-1019. 8m/s/9° 10.57/8.6° 929mb in/out cloud. 50/50 - low CN (AMS) counts of CVI inlet - out of cloud. NOW starts near coral
13:36:08	R8 end	2500		51.8/1.3E	8m/s/328. 10.37/8.31 - climbing ↑4000'
13:56:50		4000'			Core Cals
13:41:42	R9 start	4000			end core down cals - start WAS even at 4000' - in/out of cloud
13:47:00	R9.	4000	301	52.0/0.9	9m/s/38° 8.48/5.82 875mb - gap lots of Cu cells around 7.64/8.06 10m/s/34ds
13:53:26	R9 end			52.2/0.2W	end Run S 100 CT. - looks smooth - rear camera
13:55:24		6000			Core Chem Start - AMSon Rosemont. - above CT
13:57:10					Ahead - few tumble. °. ↑ 6500' - Core Chem above
13:57:40		6500			Core Chem Cals Start
13:58:28	R10	6500		52.1/0.3W	CCN start sample - still CT's a
14:00:31		7000			GPC-2400 - CNE 1600 ? 87 52.1/ 223ms 3.5°/1.82°C 9m/s/41° 781mb
14:05:19	R10				↑ 7500'
14:05:33		7500			need to climb again → ↑800'
14:07:00		8000			still into cloud, again - climbing again
14:09:10		9000			some ice (2D)
14:10:36	R10 end				Muh!

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B109
Date : 08 Jul 2005
Operator & contact info : Doug Anderson (dougan@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	Standard gas leak, before final cal.
O₃	
NO_x	Chamber temp occ. slightly above normal
SO₂	U/s – not operated
TDLAS	Not operated
WAS	Not operated

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cal) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
08:45:53	Ground	
09:18:45	Ground	
09:34:38	Ground	
10:14:32	FL110	
11:07:27	FL015	
11:29:49	FL025	
11:33	FL030	Cal Valve quick check – no need for full cal.
11:46:40	FL040	
12:06:15	FL070- FL065	Cal invalid by early descent
12:13:37	FL107 – FL025	Cal invalid by ascent
12:21:10	?	Cal Valve quick check – no need for full cal.
12:40:21	FL055	
12:44:30	FL060	Cal Valve quick check – no need for full cal.
13:05:52	FL010	
13:22:10	FL025	Cal Valve quick check – no need for full cal.
13:41:45	FL040	
13:5?	FL060	Cancelled due to cal gas leak
14:00:41	FL065- FL007	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. 8/7/05

Date: 8/09

Operator: P. P. J.

Page of

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP			2D2-C			HVPS or 2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
1029	90	0.09	1270										Start P ₁ @ 110
1031	170	0.1	1270										@ 080
103240	240	0.1	1270										070
103335	280	0.1	1270										060
103435	270	0.1	1270										050
103727	320	0.09	1270										040
103827	600	0.1	1273										030
103925	700	0.1	1276										020
104030	530	0.2	1422				140	25	12				010
10521													Start P ₂ @ 020
105614	600	0.1	2637										1000
105716													end P ₂ @ 200hr
100813													Start P ₁ @ 1800hr
1100	650	0.09											
1112	650	0.09	3466										
1114	550	0.09	3466										
1116	580	0.09	3466										
1118	600	0.09	3466										
1120	600	0.09	3466										
112219													- end Run 1
112656													Start Run 2 @ 025
1128	600	0.09	3466										
1130	500	0.09	3466										
1132	600	0.09	3466										
1134	550	0.13	3505										
1136	640	0.1	3527										
1138	600	0.09	3534										
1140	600	0.10	3534										
114046													end Run 2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. *B09*

Date: *8/7/05*

Operator: *PAJS*

Page 2 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP <i>SID</i>			2D2-C			HVPS or 2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
114622	400	0.09	3717		1000							Start run 3
1148	400	0.1	3836		3000							
1150	450	0.1	3920		100							
1152	480	0.09	3921		70							
1154	500	0.09	3921		20							
1156	400	0.1	3935		1000							
115725												end run 3
120541	130	0.09	4255		-							Start run 4
120635	230	0.09	4255		-							Start P3 @ 070
120740	200	0.08	4257		5000							060
120840	400	0.12	4308		100							050
120920	400	0.2	4404		6000							040
120008	400	0.3	5796		6000							030
121033												020
1212	350	0.2	5769		6000							- end P2 Start P4
1214	350	0.2	5761		6000							
1216	400	0.1	5973		60							
121758												- end run 4
122246	350	0.13	6792		50							Start run 5
122424	400	0.1	6837		3000							FSSP failed
122628	450	0.1	229		5000							
1230	350	0.19	923		6000							
1232	300	0.2	1230		6000							
1234	300	0.2	1905		6000							
123454												- end run 5
124036	200	0.09										Start run 6
1242	140	0.2	2611		6000							
1244	230	0.09										
1246	220	0.09										
1248	170	0.09	2770		10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B1009

Date: 8/7/05

Operator: PAPP

Page 3 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP <i>SID</i>			2D2-C			HVPS or 2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
125640	500	0.1	2890		1000	20	600	1	20	600	1	030
125740	600	0.2	3078		6000	100	200	1				020
125928												end photo
130053												start run 7 PS.
130120	650	0.09										010
130207												end of PS
130509	400	0.09	3489		10.							Start run 7
1307	400	0.09	3489		10							
1309	400	0.08	"									
1311	420	0.09	"									
1313	400	0.09	"									
1315	400	0.09	"									
1317	300	0.09	"									
131731												- end Run 7
132403	340	0.09										Start run 8
1326	420	0.1	4019		20							
1328	360	0.09	4033		10							
1330	400	0.09	4037		10							
1332	540	0.09	4044		10							
1334	520	0.09	4049		1000							
1336	400	0.1	4161		100							
133609												- end Run 8
134144	260	0.09	4264		100							Start Run 9
1344	260	0.1	4351		1000							
1346	270	0.09	4354		100							
1348	300	0.1	4425		100							
1350	360	0.1	4425		100							
1352	250	0.2	5168		3000							
135326												- end of Run 9
135828	150	0.08	5414									Start run 10
1401	120	0.1	5414									
1404	80	0.1	5414									
1407	60	0.09	5539		10.							

141039 - end of Run 10

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B109

Date: 08/07/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	Y Y	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	Y	CONDOR
3) Log on to FLOODS run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_output_binary a) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	Complete, no errors. *.txt files deleted after B109 and B109A files
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	Y	
4) run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_extract_tas a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	0 240000	Completed
5) run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_read a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	Y Y Y 0 Y	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL15072005.txt Completed for B109 and B109A files
6) In PVWAVE a) .run mrfb:[pms.proc]ffssp_sec_read .run mrfb:[pms.proc]lag b) .run mrfb:[pms.proc]write_procffssp_to_m5 c) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format d) exit	Y	Lag of -7 secs corrected for using JW for file B109 Lag of -9 secs corrected for using JW for file B109A Completed
7) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name	Y	Completed (left as mfd)

			log so set at 0.
e) TAS:	Y	Y	
f) MFD directory:	MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	Y	
g) Probe number:	(1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty	0	
h) Start time:	0 if unkown	0	
i) End time:	240000 if unknown	240000	
j) Nominal averaging:	0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	0.2	
k) Particle type:	8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown	8	CLOPAP flight so interested in water cloud. However, quick look images showed ice particles for certain sections of the flight so selected 8
l) Coefficient choice:	2	2	
m) Output root filename:	PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	Y	Completed
10) In PVWAVE			
i) .run MRFB:[PMS.PROC]WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5			
ii) write_proc2d_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_proc2d.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2d'			
iii) exit		Y	Completed
11) MODIFY			
a) Modifying datasets:	pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D		
b) Datset:	mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX		
c) New dataset:	Enter modified MFD name	Y	Completed (left as mfda)

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B109

Date: 08/07/2005

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm3/sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: 0 if unknown h) End time: 240000 if unknown	1 0.7 0 0 240000	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate B104 = 0.8, B110 = 0.6 Do not have cloud physics log for B109 so set at 0.7 Do not have cloud physics log so set at 0 Completed
3) In PVWAVE i) .run MRFB:[PMS.PROC]WRITE_PROCPCASP_TO_M5 ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' , 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' iii) exit	Y	Completed
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	Y	Completed. MFD renamed as B109_mfdb

Flight No 109

CCNC LOG

Exp. QOPAP

Date 8/7/05

Page 1 of 2

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	Dyn	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5		
11:12:11	11:12:20	27.6 27.08	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5			
Run 1			0.46	0.68					S	
			889						D	
			1703	955					B	
			2188	2187					R	
			1000.6	1000.6					P	
11:12:11	11:12:20	29.1	0.45	0.66	1.0	1.3	1.90		S	
Run 2			29.1	919	1022	1030	3231	3210	D	
			28.98	917	2029	1060	1112	1233	B	
			28.8	2217	2213	2240	2275	2322	R	
			28.7	1000.6	1000.6	1000.5	1000.5	1000.6	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
11:27:10	27:40	29.1	0.46	0.69	1.02	1.31	1.94		S	
Run 2			28.06	1554	1792	2112	3036	2703	D	
			27.9	1053	1053	1057	1057	1077	B	
			27.9	2202	2210	2219	2236	2280	R	
			28.0	1000.1	1000.3	1000.2	1000.2	1000.3	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
"	"	27.69	0.46	0.68	1.02	1.33	1.93		S	
Run 2			28.04	1773	1807	2352	2651	2809	D	
			27.71	1079	1079	1079	1086	1099	B	
			27.53	2277	2273	2286	2301	2305	R	
			27.5	1000.2	1000.3	1000.1	1000.2	1000.3	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
11:45:28	11:45:57	27.77	0.44	1.68	1.03	1.34	1.96		S	
Run 3			27.8	1426	1174	1054	2510	1314	D	
			27.5	1110	1113	1081	1081	1070	B	
			26.69	2325	2329	2318	2299	2290	R	
			26.6	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
12:40:02	12:40:32								S	
Run 6									D	
									B	
									R	
									P	

2 saturation peak not 2+3 found but no peak seen on funnel display

failed in cloud

Flight No 109

CCNC LOG

Exp. CCOPAP

Date 8/7/05

Page 1 of 2

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	Dyn	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
11:12:11	11:12:20		27.6	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			27.08	0.46	0.68				S
			889						D
			1703	955					B
			2188	2187					R
			1000.6	1000.6					P
11:12:11	11:12:20		29.1	0.45	0.66	1.0	1.3	1.90	S
			29.1	0.49	1022	1030	3231	3210	D
			28.98	0.47	2629	1060	1112	1233	B
			28.8	2217	2213	2240	2276	2322	R
			28.7	1000.6	1000.6	1000.5	1000.5	1000.6	P
11:27:16	27:40			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			29.1	0.46	0.69	1.02	1.31	1.94	S
			28.06	1554	1792	2112	3036	2703	D
			27.9	1053	1053	1057	1057	1077	B
			27.9	2202	2210	2219	2236	2240	R
			28.0	1000.1	1000.3	1000.2	1000.2	1000.3	P
"	"		27.69	0.46	0.68	1.01	1.33	1.93	S
			28.04	1773	1807	2352	2651	2809	D
			27.71	1079	1079	1079	1086	1099	B
			27.53	2277	2273	2286	2301	2305	R
			27.5	1000.2	1000.3	1000.1	1000.2	1000.3	P
11:45:28	11:45:57			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			27.71	0.44	0.68	1.03	1.34	1.96	S
			27.8	1426	1174	1054	2510	1314	D
			27.5	1110	1113	1081	1081	1070	B
			26.69	2325	2329	2318	2299	2290	R
			26.6	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	P
12:40:02	12:40:32			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			27.71	0.44	0.68	1.03	1.34	1.96	S
			27.8	1426	1174	1054	2510	1314	D
			27.5	1110	1113	1081	1081	1070	B
			26.69	2325	2329	2318	2299	2290	R
			26.6	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	P
			27.71	0.44	0.68	1.03	1.34	1.96	S
			27.8	1426	1174	1054	2510	1314	D
			27.5	1110	1113	1081	1081	1070	B
			26.69	2325	2329	2318	2299	2290	R
			26.6	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	P
			27.71	0.44	0.68	1.03	1.34	1.96	S
			27.8	1426	1174	1054	2510	1314	D
			27.5	1110	1113	1081	1081	1070	B
			26.69	2325	2329	2318	2299	2290	R
			26.6	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	1000.3	P

R 5/15/05

Run 1

Run 2

Run 2

Run 3

Run 6

Climbed for 4 25

2 saturation peak net 2+3 found but no peak seen on found display

failed in cloud

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B109
Date: 08/07/2005

Campaign Name: CLOPAP
Operator: J. Hopkins, R. Boddy (York)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
10:00:47			Take off Cranfield	
~ 10:05			Turn on WAS pump and compressed air	(3.23)
~ 10:11			FL110 (Noxy cals)	
10:29:00			FL110 start profile 1	(3.06)
			Interrupted	
10:36:33			Resume profile 1 (descending)	
10:40:50			Interrupted at ~1200 ft... (missed approach at Coltishall)	
10:55:51			Start profile 2 (2000 ft)	
10:57:16			End profile 2	
11:08:13			Start Run 1 1500 ft (between cloud)	
11:10:56	11:11:56	1	Run 1 (not in cloud)	3.36
11:14:47	11:15:47	33	Run 1 (not in cloud)	3.36
11:19:17	11:20:17	2	Run 1 (not in cloud)	3.36
11:22:19			End run 1; ascending	
11:26:56			Start run 2 (partly in cloud) 2700 ft	
11:31:15	11:32:15	3	Run 2 (climbing to 3000 ft towards end of fill; coming into cloud)	3.30
11:34:36	11:35:36	34	Run 2 at 3000 ft	3.30
11:37:30	11:38:30	4	Run 2 at 3000 ft (v. broken cloud)	3.30
11:40:46			end run 2 (approx. 3200 ft)	
11:46:14	11:47:14	5	Fast Fill (in response to AMS information)	
11:46:20			Start run 3 (7000 ft)	
11:47:46	11:48:46	6	Fast Fill (in response to AMS information)	3.27
11:50:41	11:51:41	35	Run 3 Normal fill in and out of cloud	3.27
11:53:33	11:54:33	7	Run 3 Normal fill in and out of cloud	3.27
11:57:29			End run 3	
12:05:41			Start profile 3	
12:10:33			End profile 3 / start run 4 (approx 1900 ft)- in cloud	
12:16:19	12:17:19	8	Run 4	3.33
12:17:58			End run 4	
12:21:04	12:21:34	9	Fast Fill (30 s fill) 1700 ft in cloud leg. Plume over sea?	3.26
12:22:46			Start Run 5 1900 ft	

12:23:31	12:24:01	10	Fast Fill (30 s) Just after plume?	
12:24:13	12:24:43	11	Fast Fill (30 s) Plume?	3.35
12:26:23	12:26:53	12	Fast Fill (30 s) Plume?	
12:29:19	12:29:49	13	Fast Fill 30 s	
12:31:14	12:31:44	36	Fast Fill 30 s	3.30
12:34:54			End Run 5	
12:39:13	12:39:43	14	Fast Fill 30 s	3.18
12:40:46			Start Run 6	
12:41:11	12:41:41	15	Fast Fill 30 s	3.17
12:43:15	12:43:45	37	Fast Fill 30 s	3.15
12:45:58	12:46:28	41	Fast Fill 30 s (in cloud)	3.15
12:50:25	12:50:55	42	Fast Fill 30 s (in response to recommendations from AMS)	3.13
12:52:33			End run 6	
12:53:18			Start profile 4	
12:00:53			Start profile 5	
13:02:07			End profile 5	
13:05:09			Start run 7 (1000 ft)	
13:06:25	13:06L55	43	Fast Fill 30 s (over land beneath cloud)	3.34
13:10:01	13:10:31	38	Fast Fill 30 s (over land beneath cloud)	3.34
13:14:20	13:14:50	44	Fast Fill 30 s (over land beneath cloud)	3.33
13:17:31			End run 7	
13:23:16	13:23:46	45	Fast Fill 30 s (in response to recommendations from AMS)	3.30
13:24:03			Start run 8 (in cloud run, ~ 2500 ft)	
13:28:36	13:29:06	39	Fast Fill 30 s	3.29
13:34:53	13:35:23	46	Fast fill 30 s near end of run 8 (to catch plume?)	3.27
13:36:08			End run 8	
13:41:42			Start run 9 FL40	
13:42:18	13:42:48	47	Fast fill 30 s (plume?)	3.21
13:50:41	13:51:11	40	Fast fill 30 s	3.25
13:53:26			End run 9	
13:58:06			Start run 10 FL65	
14:02:01	14:02:31	48	Fast Fill 30 s	3.12
14:10:49			End run 10	
~ 14:44			Land Cranfield	

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 08/07/2005

FLIGHT: B109

OPERATOR: Jonny Crosier

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Power ON 0700	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓		
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓		
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓		
	Turn on: Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	✓		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓		
	Turn on Alcatel...100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓	Monitor Pump Currents	
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON...100%	Pump Control Box			
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON...100%	Pump Control Box			
	Turbo pump 6 ON...100%	Pump Control Box			
Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC				
Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓	Approx 2.8V, 0.9A		
Pre-Brief 0830	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓		
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	✓	Approx 125Hz	
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓		
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓		
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	NEGATIVE NUMBER	
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓	old = 2.475 kV	New = 2.00 kV.
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓		
	Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 08/07/2005

FLIGHT: B109

OPERATOR: Jonny Crosier

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief 0920	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	✓		
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9, AB approx 2.3MHz	All ok.
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC			
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Reconnect inlet and GRIMM	Inlet	✓		
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓	LOG CPC IN LABVIEW	
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMSVAMSCODE\AMSMENU.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓			
Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓			
General Alteration mode, Open Inlet	Software, Start after t/o	✓			

AMS PostFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 08/07/2005

FLIGHT: B109

OPERATOR: Jonny Casiver

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS, Grimm CPC logging	Software	✓		
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet	✓		
	Exit Labview		✓		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	✓		
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	✓		
	Open Inlet		✓		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Check gain at current V	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15, 16, 17, 30, 46*	
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Attach Zero filter to inlet		X		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	X	14, 16, 30, 43, 44, 46, 48, 57	
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	X		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	X		
	General alteration, 10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave	X	Check tof windows	
	Close inlet		✓		
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight			
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight			
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight			
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\ Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight			
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop				
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	ShutDown	Turn off Multiplier & Balzers	Electronics box	✓	
Turn off all Turbos and PC		Pump Controller Box			
Shut Backing Valve		Back of rack			
Turn off heater, chopper, the rest		Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers			

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 08/07/2005

FLIGHT: B109

OPERATOR: Jonny Croser.

Tuning

TIME: 0940	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	18	24	22
Def Outer	11	14	11
Heater Bias	-6.63	-6.82	-6.5
Focus	15	15.5	12.5
Extraction	226	242	220

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME: 0942	New	Typical
KV	2.475	n/a
KV Change	0.00	0.025kV
Gain	3.48e6	3.00E+06
G used Change	1.41	1

TIME: 1600	New	Typical
KV	2.475	n/a
KV Change	0	0.025kV
Gain	2.92e6	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.84	1

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME: 0950	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.133e6	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.622	4
IPP NO3	445.76	400
IPP NH4	521.30	550
Airbeam MS	7.26e6	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	7.05e6	2.00E+06
Run Number	632	n/a

TIME: 1610	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.008e6	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.694	4
IPP NO3	446.76	400
IPP NH4	500.61	550
Airbeam MS	2.51e6	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	2.22e6	2.00E+06
Run Number	1148	n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	
Run number	

TIME:	
Run number	

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 08/07/2005

FLIGHT: B109

OPERATOR: Jonny Casier

Time 0850

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.18	0.86	94	98
2	0.29	3.5	100	100
3	0.42	1	100	100
4	0.60	0.5	100	100
5	0.43	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.38	2.5
Heater I	0.93	0.9
Heater T	440	580
Heater B	0v	75V
Multiplier	0	n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	3	7A
I diaphragm	1.5	2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Time 1115

11kft.

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.75	0.86	84.6	98
2	2.95	3.5	100.5	100
3	1.29	1	100.6	100
4	0.6	0.5	100.2	100
5	0.41	0.4	100.2	100
6	0.44	0.46	100.2	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.82	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	SRS	580
Heater B	75	75V
Multiplier	2.685	n/a
Pressure	1.4	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.5	2A
MS AB	1.93	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.8	2Mhz
Flow	1.25	2

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B109**

Date: 08/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	Y
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	Y	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B109

Date: 08/07/05

Instruments

1. Video – inboard recorder screen in standby
2. SO2 out of action
3. CO cal gas leak suspected

Aircraft

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B109:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Keith Bower
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
Peroxide	No log is ever taken for Peroxide
PAN	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005):

- 2 x Forward Facing Camera
- 2 x Rearward facing Camera

